

the determination coefficient, which is the multiple correlation coefficient raised to the 2nd power:

$$F = \frac{R^2}{1-R^2} \frac{(n-m-1)}{m} \quad (17)$$

where R^2 is determination coefficient, n is observations number, m is parameters (factors) number.

The obtained value of the Fisher criterion is compared with the table value and, if it exceeds it, then the constructed model is statistically reliable. Considering that the observations number is $n=20$, and the factors number is $m=5$, we obtain the Fisher value: $F=7.14258009540836000$. Using the Fisher table for the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, for our system we obtain the tabular value $F_{Tab}=2.96$. Considering that the numerical value obtained by us is greater than the tabular one, it can be argued that the resulting regression model is quite adequate.

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PROCESS CONTROL OF CATALYTIC CRACKING

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Abstract

In the technological processes of the oil refining industry, the use of various functional apparatuses connected in various structures and the technological process continuity lead to the control complexity. Catalytic cracking plays a key role in the destructive oil refining process to meet the industry in gasoline needs. The main purpose of the catalytic cracking process is to obtain a gasoline high-octane component, but other valuable petroleum products are also obtained during this process. For this reason, one of the most important issues is the search for the optimal mode of technological process operation, the choice and justification of modern automation tools in accordance with the standards for the optimal implementation of the flow of this technological process.

Keywords: technological process, oil refining, catalytic cracking, high-octane component, vacuum distillate.

The catalytic cracking process has been deeply studied, many experimental observations have been made at various installations, and according to the studies carried out, it can be concluded that a large volume of both physical and chemical process flows is observed within this complex [1÷3].

One of the main blocks for the catalytic cracking unit (type "Q-43-107M") is the reactor block. This unit is used for catalytic cracking of vacuum distillate. Vacuum distillate supplied to this plant as a raw material is obtained from the primary oil refining unit, and one of the resulting oil products is vacuum distillate [4].

Currently, work is underway to modernize the Heydar Aliyev Oil Refinery plant, including the catalytic cracking unit. Since the modernization is complex,

these procedures also affect the automatic control system of this unit. Thus, the question arose about the integrated design of the automatic control system for the catalytic cracking unit. In the solving process this problem, a problems number emerged:

- low accuracy of used instrumentation and automation equipment;
- long delays in automatic tuning cycles;
- low quality of compressed air supplied to the pneumatic system.

Based on all this, we can say that it is impossible to solve the above problem using local instrumentation and automation tools that work with the existing old pneumatic automation, that is, it is impossible to create

operational control and optimal control of the catalytic cracking process simultaneously with measurements.

Thus, the fulfillment of one or another of the above requirements made it possible to use the TDC-3000 automated control system manufactured by the American company Honeywell.

"TDC-3000" is an automatic control system that solves the most complex issues of control and management for the technological processes at industrial objects. Automatic control system "TDC-3000" is multi-stage. One of these steps is the direct control of the technological process, that is, the control actions obtained as a result of collecting and processing data from all primary transmitters to the processor are sent directly to the actuators.

At the highest level, tasks requiring high-precision calculation are provided through this system. The main functions performed by the TDC-3000 Automatic Control System are as follows:

- control of the process by the operator through one window;

- process management and system monitoring;
- system setup;
- finding a process engineer in direct contact with the system;
- creation of an opportunity for employees of the system service to monitor it;
- monitoring and diagnosing problems that the system cannot diagnose by a process engineer;
- construction of a mathematical model for the technological process, optimization of control and planning.

When developing the program for displaying data in the control system, standard software packages offered by Honeywell were used. The system is only adapted for data entry software. In this case, standard software is used [5÷10].

Automatic Control System "TDC-3000" (Fig. 1) uses powerful 18- and 32-bit processors. The use of such powerful microprocessors is necessary to solve very complex manufacturing processes. Automatic Control System "TDC-3000" as a whole looks like this:

Fig. 1. "TDC-3000" architecture

- universal station provides process control through a single window;
- the unit operator and other structures associated with the process ensure high performance and system protection;
- the interconnection of all the system structures is ensured by means of a coaxial cable for the transmission of all instructions and data;
- system module (LCN) connected locally.

Since oil refining processes consist of complex interconnected devices with different functions, chemical reactions take place inside them, these processes are accompanied by high temperature and high pressure. For this reason, in addition to buying a quality product, safety is considered an important issue. In order to ensure the device safety, it is proposed to use Automatic Protection Systems, Automatic Blocking and Alarms in accordance with modern standards. It is more expedient to use modern control systems with a preventive effect - Safe Structured Systems for the safe management of technological processes, the workers health, the materials and equipment safety.

It should be noted that as a introduction result of the TDC-3000 system into production, there was no need to use hundreds of pneumatic machines, thousands of cables meters and copper pipes (small diameter). It was the introduction of this system into production that ensured the stable and reliable operation for the catalytic cracking unit, improving the quality of the resulting petroleum products and increasing their quantity.

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